

Data Science in the Combat against Desertification

Utilization of Machine Learning in Desertification and Land Degradation Assessment and Prediction

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Figure 1: Aral Sea 2000 vs. 2018, including the original border of 1960. [18]

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Abstract:

Desertification is a complex issue mainly caused by land degradation through human impact. It has a negative effect on ecosystems, climate change and food production, forcing migration. With growing population, this issue will only increase and potentially affect more than 3 billion people, according to the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD). Therefore, Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) assessment and also prediction is needed to aid the combat against desertification and land degradation. Several Machine Learning methods are used to facilitate Natural Scientist in their endeavors to map, assess and predict LULC. However, unified methods and indices would be beneficial to develop the field and improve large scale assessment.

Keywords:

Desertification, Land Degradation, Machine Learning, Prediction, Global Desertification Index Standard

1 Introduction

Desertification is a global problem affecting potentially half of the world's population [11]. Desertification causes degradation of ecosystems, destroying habitats and depriving the living foundation of many, resulting amongst other in migration [11]. It remains one of the major environmental issues of the 21st century and will increase along with growing population and accelerating climate change [1, 2, 3].

There are many definitions for desertification containing various aspects, but all definitions involve the phenomenon of land degradation affected by different factors [2]. The United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD) handles for example the definition of Kannan (2012):

“Desertification is land degradation in arid, semi-arid, and dry sub-humid areas resulting from various factors, including climatic variations and human activities. It remains potentially the most threatening ecosystem change impacting the socio-economic conditions of millions of people living in the drylands, which account for a significant proportion of the Earth's land. It is caused by complex interactions of a number of physical, biological, political, social, cultural, and economic factors. Generally, it is a detrimental process that brings about a gradual and an unnoticed reduction in the productive capacity of land over a period of years.” [12]

Desertification emerges as a manmade problem, often combined with climate change, which is in turn also a manmade problem with cause and effect in interaction, which means desertification is not only a result of climate change, but can also impact acceleration of climate change – a vicious circle [11]. There are several ways of combating desertification. The UNCCD is actively involved in sharing knowledge and concepts to reverse desertification [11]. Often, the issue in combating desertification lies in a lack of funds and resources.

To be effective and use resources efficiently, focus must shift on the identification of areas that are vulnerable to desertification [3]. Predicting the evolution of land degradation can help to protect soil and biodiversity, prevent negative impact on climate change and secure food production for the (local) population [5]. Additionally, it is also important to assess desertification and identify responsible factors and not only evaluate sensitivity or susceptibility to desertification [3].

The partial disappearance of the Aral Sea (Fig. 1) demonstrates, what can happen if authorities ignore negative changes over a period of time, leading into catastrophic scenarios and irreversible damage, affecting the lives of many for a long period. LULC changes are dynamic and unavoidable, particularly in developing countries. Therefore, it is important to identify appropriate methods and approaches that can predict or simulate future LULC, also considering different scenarios [9].

2 Objectives and methodology

Data Science is on the rise and used in all scientific fields including the Natural Science. The aim of this paper is to assess how and to what extent Machine Learning is applied in the combat against desertification and how it contributes in the assessment of Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) change. Analyzing, modelling and understanding the transformation of LULC is crucial to avoid desertification [7]. One of the main issues is the complexity of the matter:

“Seeing the tipping point after the fact and ascribing mechanisms to the change is one thing; predicting them using empirical data has been a challenge. The difficulty in predicting tipping points stems from the large number of species and interactions (high dimensionality) within ecological systems, the stochastic nature of the systems and their drivers, and the uncertainty and importance of initial conditions that the nonlinear nature of the systems introduce to outcomes” [10].

The method used in this paper is a literature study, focusing on recent papers in the field of desertification or LULC assessment and mainly prediction. It aims to give a basic overview of the latest findings, not to go in-depth in the mathematics and explain algorithm formula's.

3 Background and results

To predict desertification or LULC change in any area, mapping and assessment of the current situation in the respective area is needed. Different mapping techniques have been used for the assessment of desertification and data collection. One of the main techniques applied is remote sensing [3].

3.1 Remote Sensing

Remote sensing is based on satellite images that are then processed by including geometric correction, atmospheric correction, image enhancement and interpretation [14]:

“Image enhancement is the process of making an image more interpretable for a particular application. Enhancement makes important features of raw, remotely sensed data more interpretable to the human eye. Enhancement techniques are often used instead of classification techniques for feature extraction studying and locating areas and objects on the ground and deriving useful information from images.” [14]

Thanks to remote sensing, high-resolution and multi-spectral data are available for many environmental monitoring applications, but for desertification assessments remote sensing can only provide indicators or estimates of land degradation, it cannot actually assess the degree of land or soil degradation processes that play a role in desertification. Processes or phenomena such as wind and water erosion or large-scale dust storms can occur that do not match the remote sensing data [5]. E.g., vegetation degradation data used to assess LULC rely mostly on remotely sensed data, but

quantitative data of the actual soil degradation processes and soil productivity losses in the drylands are scarce [5].

3.2 Evaluation Indicators

One approach to evaluate desertification are various geographical, geomorphological, socio-economic, droughtiness, soil condition and other evaluation scales or indicators. Often, they are compiled and are used as input variables for prediction models. These are found in many scientific articles and papers and some are also applied by the UNCCD. Here some examples:

3.2.1 Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI)

The Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI) is a multiscalar drought index based on climatic data. It can be used for determining the onset, duration and magnitude of drought conditions with respect to normal conditions in a variety of natural and managed systems such as crops, ecosystems, rivers, water resources, etc. and can help to analyze the dynamic process of land desertification at different levels [1, 17].

3.2.2 Normalized Vegetation Index (NDVI)

The Normalized Vegetation Index (NDVI) is obtained by remote sensing image data and is used for determining spatial distribution of vegetation growth. The greater the NDVI, the denser the vegetation; the smaller the NDVI, the more sparse the vegetation [1].

3.2.3 Global Desertification Vulnerability Index (GDVI)

The Global Desertification Vulnerability Index (GDVI) is a compiled index that tries to catch the complexity of desertification. It is compiled from the Human Activity Index (HAI), which is used to estimate the influence of human activity. It is constructed on the basis of four human indicators: population density, population growth, CO₂ emissions, and GDP. The next index to create the GDVI is the Climate Environment Index (CEI), based on Leaf Area Index, Aridity Index and Temperature Anomaly over time [13].

3.2.4 MEDALUS

MEDALUS stands for Mediterranean Desertification and Land Use and is used mainly in Europe to identify the sensitivity of land to desertification. The method requires the collection of data to create four main quality indices: soil, climate, vegetation, and management and are divided into Soil Quality Index (SQI), Climate Quality Index (CQI), Vegetation Quality Index (VQI) and Grazing Quality Index (GQI)[2]. The MEDALUS approach is widely used, also outside Europe, but it focuses mainly on the physical loss of soil by water erosion in European Mediterranean environments, while the phenomenon of desertification in semi-arid areas results from both, the natural environment and socio-economic conditions [3].

3.3 Machine Learning

Machine learning algorithms have emerged as efficient alternatives in large scale mapping. A variety of techniques such as classification and regression trees, artificial neural networks, k-nearest neighbors, logistic regression, support vector machines, and random forest models (RFM) were tested in natural resources mapping. These machine learning techniques are mostly used in digital soil mapping and are most common in LULC classification [4, 14].

Image classification to obtain LULC information is one thing, but there are only limited studies available on use of machine language classifiers in land degradation, desertification mapping or desertification prediction [4].

Here some promising attempts:

3.3.1 Logistic Regression

Logistic regression is frequently used in the field of Natural Sciences, earth science and ecology are no exception to this. It is a method used in remote sensing for change detection in land cover, soil-landscape modelling and prediction of post-fire soil erosion. As it has been extensively used for landslide susceptibility mapping, it has been adapted for use in desertification mapping, as both are natural hazards controlled by numerous variables and are characterized by non-linearity [3]. The advantage of the logistic regression is that it can handle a mixture of numerical and categorical variables and also evaluate the contribution of each factor to a phenomenon and determine the most influential factors. Furthermore, the estimation of the odds ratio provides information on the strength and direction of the association between the dependent variable and the independent variables [3].

Input data, such as geomorphic factors, are mainly derived from satellite images and calibrated and put into maps. Further maps with environmental and socioeconomic prediction factors are created, not only based on satellite images, but also maps based on older images (to compare LULC change), lithological maps or even self created maps with relevant information or data added (see figures 2 and 3). Crucial is that the pixels of each map are matched to each other as these pixels are the used and split into train and test set. The prediction is also pixel by pixel indicating desertification risk or not [3].

Djeddaoui et al. were using this approach for studying a specific area in Algeria and came to a prediction accuracy of 87.8 % (AUC/ROC = 0.878) [3]. With almost 45 % of the studied area susceptible to desertification, this information is valuable in the decision making of local authorities, when it comes to taking measures and choosing a strategy to mitigate desertification. However, the study also clearly indicates, that a lot of domain knowledge and understanding of the local circumstances is needed. Field work was done in this study to gain and verify certain data for some variables, indicating that automation or automatized procedures and methods in this area is not reached yet [3].

Figure 2: Maps of the environmental and socioeconomic prediction factors: (A) precipitation; (B) normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI); (C) rural population; (D) livestock density; (E) land cover; (F) drainage distance; (G) drainage density; and (H) evapotranspiration. [3]

Figure 3: Maps of the geomorphological and soil prediction factors: (A) land surface temperature (LST); (B) elevation; (C) hypsometric integral (HI); (D) curvature; (E) lithology; (F) slope; (G) topographic position index (TPI); and (H) aspect. [3]

3.3.2 Random Forrestr

Also the Random Forrestr Method (RFM) has been used for the purposes of desertification detection. Dharumarajan et al. explored the possibility of assessing small regions for desertification and the potential for extrapolating the results to larger regions. Similar to Logistic Regression, the RFM has the advantage that it can handle a large number of quantitative and categorical data [4]. The RFM can also indicate the most influential factors, since it selects the most important predictor at each node split [4]. Also in this case, a validation method assessing the prediction performance of the model was needed and based on datasets developed from previous desertification status mapping projects as a reference [4]. Several indices are separately integrated in the form of spatial layers and form the input data in form of pixels again split in training and test sets, validated against the prepared desertification status map. The accuracy reached was 71 %.

3.3.3 Artificial neural networks (ANN)

Habibi et al. used Artificial neural networks (ANN) to predict the level of groundwater as it can also be used in monitoring desertification and land degradation. Analogue to the

MEDALUS, Iran uses the Iranian Model of Desertification Potential Assessment (IMDPA), which consists of nine criteria including climate, water and irrigation, land and geomorphology, soil, erosion (water and wind), vegetation, agriculture, economic and social, industrial and urban development scored according to their role in desertification. Groundwater level decline belongs to the water and irrigation criterion and was predicted using monthly rainfall, topographic wetness index, distance of the river (m), latitude and longitude of Piezometers as input variables. The prediction performance of the ANN was evaluated with an efficiency of $R^2=0.96$ and $MSE=0.71$, where latitude and longitude of the Piezometers had the highest effects (29 and 34 %) and the amount of precipitation had second highest effect in the selected model [6].

3.3.4 Cellular Automata Markov Chains (CA-Markov)

As mentioned, the mapping of dynamic LULC change is complicated. A promising method, as it considers dynamic changes and at the same time is able to make some accurate future predictions, is the integrated Cellular Automata Markov Chain (CA-Markov) known as a capable estimator [9].

Cellular Automata (CA)

Briefly explained, CA is a mathematical model coming from the computational and automata theory and consist of a grid with cells in a finite number of states, changing over time and with an effect on and of nearest neighbor cell values. CA tends to make homogeneous states and produces self-similar patterns, as the rule for updating the state of cells is the same for each cell and does not change over time, and is applied to the whole grid simultaneously. These changes might be happening in the center of a group of cells or at the border. CA can be combined with other models, such as the Markov Chain. In this case, the Markov Chain is used to update not only the state of the cells, but also for updating the (otherwise fixed) rule for updating the cells. In CA, the grid have any finite number of dimensions, in the case of LULC, it is used as a map in 2D [9, 16].

Markov Chain

Markov Chains are used to predict a future state by the use of transition matrices, with the use of transition probabilities. A current state or initial point is defined and this point is independent from the past. In LULC studies, each identified class might remain the same for a long time and some of them change to another class.

The Markov chain is a sequence of random (stochastic) processes in which the result of each process at any given time depends only on the result of the process next to it [7, 9].

CA-Markov

The CA-Markov model is the combination of Cellular Automata and transition probability matrix and solves the problem, as a CA model alone is not capable of incorporating different dimensions of the environment into the simulation.

CA-Markov chain can simulate two-way transitions among any number of categories and can predict any transition among any number of categories transitional probabilities several LULCs in different time spans [7, 9].

CA-Markov applied for LULC determination and future prediction

To use the CA-Markov, at least two sets of (satellite) images covering the same area over a different time span in the past are needed. For classification to determine the different LULC zones, Random Forrest or Support Vector Machines (SVM) can be used, as these have a nearly 100 % accuracy providing pixel by pixel analysis. Only major LULC are considered. Then major LULC changes are used to determine the transition matrix probabilities, expressing the overall probability that for the region observed between two (or more) periods, basically by evaluating net gains and net losses experienced by main spatial class changes (e.g. grassland into desert). In parallel with observing the class changes, their location should also be considered. This is why the CA part is important, as it treats the maps as a grid with cells and uses the transition matrix to calculate the changes in their locations. With this method, also future states can be predicted. Case studies indicate an accuracy of more than 80 %. (e.g. LULC prediction in some areas in Iran and Iraq) [7, 9].

4 Discussion

Desertification is a complex process and is the result of many different combined factors, such as biophysical and socioeconomic factors including climate, terrain, soil and human pressure [4]. Desertification status mapping is a enormous task carried out by Natural Scientists of different fields and specializations all over the world [4]. Predicting desertification is even more complex, as predictive factors used to assess desertification may vary from one region to another [3] and as there is no unified method for prediction variables or no global standard desertification index. Also, the totality of interactions and processes that determine the landscapes are impossible to simulate numerically as of today [8] and LULC change detection techniques are often criticized, because the observed changes can be related to other factors than the ones under study [3], therefore, desertification is perceived as a local-scale degradation problem. A multidisciplinary approach based on biophysical and socioeconomic factors is required to detect areas vulnerable to desertification [4].

Machine learning methods are commonly used in desertification detection, mainly as a useful tool in the of support mapping, e.g. by applying classification for data gained by remote sensing [3]. Several mathematical models and machine learning algorithms have been developed to allocate vulnerable desertification areas [4]. Still, it would be beneficial to combine several machine learning methods in the same locations for comparison and unify assessment and

data collection methods, to perform desertification detection on a large scale.

5 Conclusion

The role of science in the global desertification discussion is crucial. Common definitions and broadly accepted research methods are needed to provide meaningful information about desertification. Large-scale assessments have focused so far mainly on vegetation cover changes, as a substitute for land degradation, not considering the complexity of the matter. Therefore, more work should be done on mapping and classification of the severity of actual soil degradation processes occurring in drylands to lead to better and more objective global assessments and better predictions of the state and changes of drylands [5].

Nevertheless, mapping at the required scale at regular intervals with high accuracy is always a challenging, time consuming, and costly affair also largely due to large amount of experts and expertise needed. Machine Learning helps to decrease the cost of these methods and contribute mainly to use resources to combat desertification efficiently and effectively.

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